

ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY IN THE BACKWATERS OF THE PULICHINTALA PROJECT ON THE KRISHNA RIVER, SURYAPET DISTRICT, TELANGANA, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The present study has been carried out to analysed. The Physico-Chemical parameter of the water quality of Krishna River in Pulichintala Project Suryapet District for take water sample use three stations, which are Station-I, Station-II and Station-III during the March 2022 to February 2024. Two years in three stations three sample take each station for water quality analysis. The total storage of water about 46 Tmcft (activation capacity 36.23Tmcft) for study. Following Physico-Chemical parameter has been used to water quality such as- Temperature, Rainfalls, P^H, Carbonates (CO₃), Bicarbonates (HCO₃), Chloride (Cl), Dissolved oxygen (DO), Sulphates (SO₄), Fluorides (F), Magnesium (Mg), Calcium (Ca), Potassium (K⁺) and Nitrate (NO₃). The results broadly indicate that the quality of water varied considerably from one location to the other and seasonal variations of water quality is present in sample on analysed.

KEYWORDS: Water quality, Physico-Chemical parameter, Krishna River, Pulichintala Project.

INTRODUCTION

Water is an integral constituent of life, and is one of the important natural resources. The present domain of life existing on the earth originated and has evolved from water. Rivers are the major life supporting systems but are facing ecological degradation these days, due to anthropogenic activities.^[1] The undesirable activities and unscientific utilization of resources from the rivers have caused environmental problems, thus threatening the biodiversity sustained by them. It is again important to note that these species-rich aquatic ecosystems are capable of self-maintaining; however, the delicate equilibrium is sensitive to external stimuli such as human activities promoted by socio economic goals.^[2] Exercising a control on the prevailing anthropogenic is necessary to sustain these socio-economically and bio aesthetically important aquatic ecosystems. Quality of water is important for drinking, irrigation, fish production, recreation and other purposes. The water quality deterioration in reservoirs usually results from acidification, heavy metal contamination, organic pollution, obnoxious fishing practices and excessive nutrient input that leads to eutrophication. The effects of these imports into the reservoir not only affect the socio-economic functions of the reservoir negatively, but also lead to the loss of structural biodiversity of the reservoir.^[3]

The present investigation studies the water quality of the Krishna River, at the Pulichintal project Suryapet District, using various water quality parameters monitored over a period of two years at three stations of the river namely station -I, station -II and station -III. Present study stretch area is 46 Tmcft of water of this river in Pulichintal project. The Pulichintala project, which is a balancing reservoir with a capacity of 46 tmcft, does not have its own ayacut, but strengthens the ayacut under the Prakasam barrage. The project does not have distributary canals. if the Pulichintala project becomes a reality, the ayacut under Prakasam barrage need not depend on release of water from Nagarjuna Sagar during nursery and transplantation of paddy periods. thanks to the lower levels of water in Nagarjuna Sagar in August and September this year coupled with inadequate water in the Prakasam barrage reservoir, transplantation of paddy in Guntur and Krishna district was delayed and the area under the paddy shrank. The Pulichintala project will augment water in the Prakasam barrage reservoir. the surplus water impounded in the Pulichintala reservoir will be released to the Prakasam barrage reservoir. with rapid development of 22 lakh acre command area under the Nagarjuna Sagar project and construction of dams in the upper reaches of Krishna River in Karnataka and Maharashtra, inflows into the Prakasam barrage have been dwindling, dislocating the agricultural operations in the Krishna delta. incidentally, the proposed project

will reduce the road length between Chennai and Hyderabad by about 40 km and improves water table in parts of Guntur and Nalgonda districts adjoining the reservoir. on the debit side, it submerges villages in Guntur district and 10 Nalgonda district affecting 5,248 families. the villages which are likely to be affected include Pulichintala, Kolluru, Chityala, Bodanam, Govindapuram, Rajulagadda and Bhimavaram in Guntur district and Nemapuri, Vellaturu, Tammavaram, Krishnapuram and Mattapalli in Nalgonda district. Pedakurapadu MLA K. Lakshmi Narayana has refuted the charge that he is opposed to the project which is in his constituency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Dr. K. L. Rao Sagar Pulichintala Project is a balancing reservoir constructed across the Krishna river near Pulichinta Village, Bellamkonda (M) in Guntur District (85.0 Km upstream of Prakasam barrage and 115.0 Km downstream of Nagarjuna Sagar Dam), for storing 45.77 TMC of water for stabilization of existing ayacut of 13.08 Lakh acres of the Krishna delta and for early transplantation of paddy crop during June and July.

Study area

Pulichintala Project is located in Suryapet District in Telangana. The water samples were collected for a period of 2 years (March-2022 to February-2024) to assess the quality of water. For this purpose, three sampling stations have been selected. Station-I is situated right side of the lake. Station-II is located middle of the bund. Station-III is situated left side of the dam. Water samples were collected from all the stations at monthly intervals and analysed for various Physico-Chemical parameters following the standard methods.^[4] One liter of surface water sample was collected from three different stations of the lake and were kept in the sedimentation column after adding 2-3 ml of 4% formaldehyde solution. The samples were kept undisturbed for about one month for complete settling of the organisms. The samples were concentrated to 100 ml Finally the concentrated material was used for frequency measurement and identification of species. For frequency measurement of different species of algae at each station, the drop method of was followed.^[5]

The samples were analysed of water quality Temperature, Rainfalls, P^H, Carbonates(CO₃), Bicarbonates (HCO₃), Chloride (Cl), Dissolved oxygen (DO), Sulphates (SO₄), Fluorides (F), Magnesium (Mg), Calcium (Ca), Potassium (K⁺) and Nitrate (NO₃) on the basis of the preliminary study, three sampling location were selected in the study area, water sample were

collected in two plastic bottles of 1000 ml, all samples were analysed for Physico-Chemical parameter as per procedure prescribed in standard method and instrument.

All the digital instrument like P^H meter, conductivity meter, spectra photo meter, were used according to standard method for water analysis carried out in the Botany laboratories. Department of Botany, Govt Degree College, Huzurnager, Telangana.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results broadly indicate that quality of water varied considerably from one station to another station.

Temperature: The average temperature 39.6°C was recorded in the month of May for the year 2022-23 whereas 40.3°C was recorded in the month of April 2023. Both the above months are in the summer period, the lowest temperature was recorded 26.3°C in the month of September 2022 and 30.1°C in the month of December 2023. In the present study minimum water temperature recorded in winter season and maximum surface water temperature recorded in summer season. Similar results were recorded in.^[6]

Rainfall: The highest rainfall was recorded in the month of August with 35.67cm for the year 2022-23 and there was 0.2 cm and 0.34 cm rainfall in the months of April and December for the year 2022-23 and 2023-24 the highest rainfall 17.88 cm was recorded in the month of July and 0.34 rainfall was recorded in the month of December 2023-24.

Carbonates: The highest concentration of Carbonates (CO₃) was recorded 34 mg/L was recorded in the month of January 2022-23 but for the month of August it was 13.05 mg/L for the year 2023-24 (this may be due to high rainfall), January was showing the highest 37 mg/L and minimum was recorded in the month of August 13.05 mg/L the same trend was observed for the both the years of study period. In the present investigation observed that carbonates values are low when compared with bicarbonates. An identical observation was made by^{[7],[2],[8]}

Bicarbonates: The highest values of HCO₃ were recorded in the month of October 262.22 mg/L for the year 2022-23 and minimum was recorded in the month of August 195.9 mg/L temperature Bicarbonate for the year 2023-24 (may be due to high temperature Bicarbonate must have been accumulated) the highest value of HCO₃ was recorded in the month of November 242.66 mg/L (the Bicarbonate must have been dissolved in water body) and

minimum was recorded in the month of July 155.92 mg/L. In the present study Bicarbonates are decreased in rainy season and increased during winter and summer seasons. A comparable observation was also noted by.^[9]

Chlorides: The highest Cl content was recorded in the month of May. Coinciding with the summer season when higher temperature 37.13 mg/L and the minimum value occurred in September 18.68 mg/L for the year 2022-23, the maximum Cl value occurred in May 2023-24 that is 34.67 mg/L for the both the years 2022-23 and 2023-24 A similar trend was observed with the highest Chlorides concentration recorded in the month of May and the minimum recorded in September 18.68 mg/L and 17.15 mg/L for the two years of study period respectively. In the present investigation Chlorides (Cl) content is reduced in rainy season. Similar opinion has been expressed by.^[10]

Dissolved Oxygen: It was observed the maximum 13.07mg/L was recorded in the month of January and 7.61mg/L in the month of August for the year 2022-23. The maximum DO content was recorded in the month of August 7.86 mg/L and 12.97 mg/L in the month of January for the year 2023-24 the same trend was observed for both the years (this condition is favourable for the growth of Phyto-Planktons). A plenty of DO is available for the phytoplankton's and also the other living organisms of the reservoir. In the present investigation DO ranges from 7.93 to 11.67 mg/L reduction of DO shows that presence of organic contamination same observation made shown in.^[11] DO content was higher in winter season the same trend was observed by.^[3]

Sulphates: The highest concentration of SO₄ were recorded 87.33 mg/L was recorded in the month of June 2022-23 but for the month of July it was 9 mg/L for the year 2023-24 (this may be due to high rainfall), May was showing the highest 86.66 mg/L and minimum was recorded in the month of July 9.7 mg/L the same trend was observed for the both the years of study period. In the present investigation Sulphates are recorded higher concentration during summer season and low concentration recorded during winter season. This is conformed with the findings of.^{[12],[13],[14],[15],[16]}

Fluorides: The highest values of *Fl* were recorded in the month of March 1.8 mg/L for the year 2022-23 and minimum was recorded in the month of September 0.53 mg/L temperature. The maximum *Fl* was recorded in month of June 1.57 mg/L and minimum was recorded in the month of August 0.53 mg/L for the year 2023-24. In the present study Fluorides ranges

from 0.53 mg/L to 1.57 mg/L. Fluorides is termed has double-edged showed, it excess and inadequate levels in drinking water are responsible for fluorosis.

Magnesium: The highest Mg content was recorded in the month of January this is in winter season with 28.66 mg/L and minimum was recorded in the month of June 16 mg/L for the year 2022-23, the maximum Mg content was recorded in the month of December 2023-24 that is 29.58 mg/L for the both the years 2022-23 and 2023-24 the same trend was observed highest concentration of Mg in the different months and minimum was recorded in the month of April 15.66 mg/L for the both years of study period. In the present study Magnesium content is lower when compare with Calcium content. This is in conformity with the observations of^{[17],[18],[19]} which have said that, normally the natural water contains Magnesium concentration lower when compare with calcium concentration.

Calcium: It was observed the maximum 42 mg/L was recorded in the month of May and 37 mg/L in the month of July for the year 2022-23. The maximum Ca content was recorded in the month of December 42 mg/L and 36.66 mg/L in the month of January for the year 2023-24 the same trend was observed for both the years (this condition is favourable for the growth of Phytoplankton's). A plenty of Ca is available for the Phytoplankton's and also the other living organisms of the river. The study of Calcium content is higher in November and December for both the years. This is in conformity with the observations of.^[20]

Potassium: The Potassium content was recorded in the month of June, this is in summer season with 8 mg/L and minimum was recorded in the August 3.66 mg/L for the year 2022-23, the maximum K^+ was recorded in the month of April, that is 7 mg/L for the both the years of 2023-24, the same trend was observed highest concentration of K^+ in the May and minimum K was recorded in the month of August 2.66 mg/L. In the present study average is recorded 8 mg/L. Potassium content in the water is toxic for some crops particularly sprinkler irrigation.

Nitrate: It was observed the maximum NO_3 content was 5.33 mg/L recorded in the month of August and 1.66 mg/L in the May for the year 2022-23. The maximum NO_3 content was recorded in the month of August 5 mg/L and 1.66 mg/lit in the month January for 2023-24. The same trend was observed for both year (this condition is favourable for the growth of Phytoplankton's). A plenty of NO_3 is available for the Phytoplankton's and also the other living organisms of the river. Nitrates are directly affected on the growth of phytoplankton.^[21]

High levels of nitrate concentration trigger eutrophication, pollution and also increase the growth of nuisance algae.

CONCLUSION

The study of the Krishna River across different locations revealed that the overall water quality is in poor condition. Significant variations were observed in the physicochemical parameters among the sampling sites. Higher values were recorded for Temperature, Rainfall influence, P^H, Carbonates (CO₃²⁻), Bicarbonates (HCO₃⁻), Chlorides (Cl⁻), Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Sulphates (SO₄²⁻), Fluorides (F⁻), Magnesium (Mg²⁺), Calcium (Ca²⁺), Potassium (K⁺), and Nitrates (NO₃⁻) at certain sites, indicating spatial variability and possible contamination. These elevated levels suggest that the river is subjected to various natural and anthropogenic influences, which may adversely affect its ecological health and suitability for domestic and agricultural use. Therefore, continuous monitoring and effective management strategies are essential to improve and protect the water quality of the river.

Table-1: Two years (2022-24) Average values of three stations Physico- Chemical Parameters.

All Parameters are expressed in Mg/Lt except pH and Temperature (°c).

S.NO	Physico- Chemical Parameters	Station-I	Station-II	Station-III
1	Temp ^{°C}	32.76	32.76	32.76
2	P ^H	8	7.99	8.1
3	Carbonate (CO ₃)	25.96	26.53	27.96
4	Bicarbonates (HCO ₃)	216.42	221.08	223.80
5	Chlorides (Cl)	25.29	26.46	27.70
6	Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	9.31	9.91	10.50
7	Sulphate (SO ₄)	49.11	51.07	52.70
8	Fluorides (F ⁺)	0.77	0.91	0.98
9	Magnesium (Mg)	20.38	21.40	22.28
10	Calcium (Ca)	38.75	39.95	41
11	Potassium (K)	4.62	5.62	6.5
12	Nitrate (NO ₃)	2.58	3.25	4.2

Fig-1.

Table-2: Shows average values of three stations season wise for two years 2022 -24.

S. NO.	Years	Physico- Chemical Parameters	Summer	Rainy	Winter
1	2022-24	Temp ^o C	37.32	30.26	30.71
2	2022-24	Rainfall	3.58	17.06	1.70
3	2022-24	P ^H	8.03	8.04	8.05
4	2022-24	Carbonate (CO ₃)	29.13	21.4	29.90
5	2022-24	Bicarbonates (HCO ₃)	216.03	211.81	233.45
6	2022-24	Chlorides (Cl)	32.34	22.52	24.58
7	2022-24	Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	9.24	8.72	11.75
8	2022-24	Sulphate (SO ₄)	84.95	11.01	56.91
9	2022-24	Fluorides (F ⁺)	1.42	0.55	0.68
10	2022-24	Magnesium (Mg)	18.16	19.66	26.23
11	2022-24	Calcium (Ca)	40.16	39.75	39.79
12	2022-24	Potassium (K)	5.75	5.16	5.83
13	2022-24	Nitrate (NO ₃)	2.66	4.20	3.16

Fig-2

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